

AN IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF PMKVY 3.0 IN SELECTED DISTRICTS OF GUJARAT STATE

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Abstract: Based on the primary data collected from the selected districts of Gujarat, this study assesses the effectiveness of the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 3.0 (PMKVY 3.0), a flagship initiative to enhance skill development and employability among Indian youth. Using a descriptive research design and a quantitative approach, data were collected via structured questionnaires from 465 beneficiaries of the Short-Term Training (STT) and 314 beneficiaries of the Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) under the Centrally Sponsored and State Managed (CSSM) component. Although most participants did not secure immediate employment post-training, significant improvements were observed in technical competencies, self-confidence, and personal development. The results indicate that while technical roles, such as Solar Panel Installation Technicians, command significant monthly incomes of Rs. 10,000-25,000, traditional service and craft roles predominantly occupied by women remain relegated to lower-income brackets of Rs. 4,000 or less. The study concludes that while PMKVY 3.0 supports skill acquisition and personal growth, intensified post-training employment support and structured placement mechanisms are essential for maximizing its impact on employment generation. These insights carry broad implications for policy design and implementation within national skill development frameworks.

Keywords: PMKVY 3.0, Short-Term Training (STT), Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL), Impact assessment

1. Introduction

India's aspiration to emerge as a global economic leader depends on its ability to utilize the potential of its young workforce (Thakur, 2022). Wheebox (2023) highlights encouraging progress, reporting that 50.3% of youth are highly employable, up from 46.2% in 2022. However, the growing demand for technologically skilled workers reveals a persistent gap between workforce supply and industry needs.

To address this, the Government of India launched the Skill India Mission on July 15, 2015, under the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE). The mission aims to create an integrated framework for vocational and technical education that aligns human resource

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capabilities with emerging market demands and facilitates sustainable economic growth (Government of India, undated).

The Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY), the flagship scheme of the Skill India Mission, was introduced to provide industry-relevant skill training and certification for youth. Its objective is to enhance employability, bridge industry skill gaps, and promote self-reliance in line with *Atmanirbhar Bharat* (self-reliant India). The scheme operates through a decentralized model involving State Skill Development Missions (SSDMs) and District Skill Committees (DSCs), which assess local training needs and coordinate implementation (MSDE, undated).

PMKVY 1.0 (2015-16) trained 19.86 lakh candidates nationwide. Building on its success, PMKVY 2.0 (2016-20) aimed to train 10 million youth with an outlay of Rs. 12,000 crore under three components—Short-Term Training (STT), Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL), and Special Projects (SP), benefiting over 11 million candidates by June 2022. The current phase, PMKVY 3.0 (2020-21), launched in January 2021 with enhanced district-level participation, focuses on reskilling and emerging technologies aligned with Industry 4.0. By June 2022, 6.74 lakh individuals aged 15-45 had been trained under this phase, with a budget of Rs. 948.90 crore (Lok Sabha, 2023).

While PMKVY has significantly expanded India's skill development landscape, limited empirical evidence exists on its effectiveness, particularly under PMKVY 3.0. Most assessments emphasize training numbers rather than employment outcomes, income improvement, or alignment with evolving industry demands. Furthermore, the effectiveness of decentralized implementation in addressing district-level skill gaps remains underexplored.

This study seeks to evaluate the impact of PMKVY 3.0 in selected districts of Gujarat, examining its effectiveness in improving employability, enhancing income, and bridging skill mismatches. It also identifies challenges in implementing policy. The focus is on beneficiaries of the Short-Term Training (STT) and the Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) components under the Centrally Sponsored State Managed (CSSM) structure, offering a comprehensive understanding of the scheme's ground-level impacts.

2. Literature Review

To provide background for this study, a review of the literature on previous evaluation studies is presented, with an emphasis on methodology and key conclusions. The majority of studies on the assessment of skill development or active labour market programs have been conducted in developed nations (Betcherman et al., 2004). However, some studies have also been conducted in countries such as Morocco, Peru, Colombia, the Dominican Republic, Nepal, Mexico, Argentina, and India.

A study on skill mismatches in the Indian labour market highlighted deviations in labour-intensive sectors and a shortage of skilled manpower in those areas. The study linked this shortage to a lack of job-market incentives and a mismatch between the education system and job-market requirements. The study suggested measures to correct skill gaps, such as identifying skill gaps, designing skill initiatives in high-potential sectors, and developing skill infrastructure (Roy, 2014; Mehrotra et al., 2013; MacDonald, 2013).

A study on the need to foster skilled labour in India highlighted a significant shortage of skilled labour if the current growth rate continues (Chakravarty et al., 2016). The study concluded that the main reasons for the skill shortage were a lack of awareness among students and a lack of effort by educational authorities to inculcate practical training among the students (Sharma and Sethi, 2015; Payne et al., 1996).

An experimental study of the 100 Hours to Success programme in Morocco was conducted by the International Initiative for Impact Evaluation (3ie) using a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) methodology with 871 youth. The study found a strong positive impact on participants' likelihood to maintain a savings account, and that older individuals benefited from financial knowledge and awareness training (Bausch et al., 2017).

The Projovent Job Youth Training Programme in Peru was evaluated by the Inter-American Development Bank (IADB) with 5791 individuals randomly assigned to the treatment group and 1360 to the control group. The programme had more demand than capacity and a database of interested applicants was available. The evaluation found a high long-term positive impact on formal employment (Diaz and Rosas, 2016).

An experimental evaluation of training provided by the Turkish National Employment Agency (ISKUR) found improvement in the quality of employment. Another study evaluated the impact of Jóvenes en Acción, a training programme in Colombia, with a baseline sample of 4353 participants in the treatment and control groups. The follow-up survey found that the program raised earnings and employment (Attanasio et al., 2011).

Most STT program participants had received pre-enrolment counselling, training, and training materials. However, placement assistance support needs to be buttressed. Satisfaction with the PMKVY program was observed to be good on parameters like quality of trainers, adequacy of curriculum, quality of training, infrastructure of the centre and the overall scheme, but satisfaction with placement assistance was observed to be and income of the students enrolled in the skilling programs under the scheme (NSDC, 2019).

The study analysed primary data collected from beneficiaries in different job roles across five selected states. The study found that the training significantly improved students' employability. The study also revealed different patterns across states in the profiles of trainers, trainees, and centre-heads. The study aimed to assess the impact of the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) on employability (CEPR, 2021).

The study assessed the performance of PMKVY 2.0 using various indicators, including enrolment, training, certification, placement, employability, inclusivity, and efficiency. The study also identified the gaps, challenges, and bottlenecks in the implementation of the scheme and suggested ways to improve them. The article concludes that the PMKVY has been successful in providing industry-relevant skill training to a large number of youths, especially women and disadvantaged groups, and enhancing their livelihood opportunities (IIPA, 2021).

3. Research Methodology

The study integrates quantitative and qualitative approaches to ensure methodological robustness and triangulation of findings. It evaluates the program's objectives, processes, and outcomes using a mixed-methods design that draws on both primary and secondary data.

Primary data were collected from beneficiaries (trainees enrolled under STT and RPL) and centre heads of PMKVY training centres. Quantitative data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to beneficiaries, while qualitative insights were drawn from interviews with centre heads, trainers, and officials of the Gujarat Skill Development Mission (GSDM). Secondary data, including official PMKVY and NSDE reports, supplemented the analysis.

The evaluation followed a descriptive design. Following the completion of the PMKVY 3.0 phase, which led to the closure of several training centres, telephonic interviews were conducted

to reach beneficiaries. Data were collected from participants across 33 districts of Gujarat, where a total of 3,640 candidates were enrolled in STT and 6,797 in RPL training. Districts were selected using the probability proportional to size (PPS) technique based on enrollment numbers, ensuring representativeness.

A structured questionnaire was translated into Gujarati to improve comprehension and capture demographic details, training experience, and post-training outcomes. Separate questionnaires were developed for STT and RPL beneficiaries. Interviews with centre heads and officials from GSDM were conducted to gather process-level insights and implementation bottlenecks. Semi-structured interviews with PMKVY centre heads, GSDM officials, and trainers provided insights into scheme implementation and bottlenecks, which informed the recommendations. Prior to data collection, the project director conducted training for field staff, ensuring regular communication and timely resolution of field-level challenges to minimize delays.

The sampling strategy selected eight districts with the highest certification counts: Ahmedabad, Anand, Gandhinagar, Jamnagar, Kheda, Mehsana, Rajkot, and Surat. Of 3,640 STT and 6,797 RPL beneficiaries in Gujarat, the study collected data from 779 respondents (465 for STT and 314 for RPL). This design ensured proportional representation across both training categories (see Table 1).

Table 1: District-wise Sample Selection

District	Population (STT)	Sample (STT)	Population (RPL)	Sample (RPL)
Ahmedabad	282	76	325	73
Anand	130	77	89	16
Jamnagar	312	77	123	26
Gandhinagar	9	6	126	53
Kheda	163	47	119	24
Mehsana	124	47	177	31
Rajkot	202	30	72	32
Surat	476	105	581	59
Total	1698	465	1612	314

Notes: STT - Short-term training; RPL - Recognition of prior learning. Districts were selected using the Probability Proportional to Size (PPS) method based on the total certified candidates in Gujarat under PMKVY 3.0.

To enhance inferential validity, hypotheses were framed not only around gender differences but also around other dimensions, such as employment outcomes by job roles and income variation across training types. Given the post-hoc nature of data collection, potential recall bias and non-response bias were acknowledged. Telephonic surveys, while practical, may have limited contextual richness and restricted observation of workplace application of skills. The absence of a pre- and post-training comparative framework further constrained causal interpretation. These methodological considerations have been explicitly factored into the analysis and discussion.

4. Secondary Data Analysis: Gujarat Skill Development Mission

Gujarat Skill Development Mission (GSDM) was established in February 2009 to coordinate the State-level strategy and programmes for skill development leading to employment. The main aim of this mission is to collect information on a comprehensive picture of all skill development programmes in the state, by analysing the skills, areas, and beneficiary groups of candidates under various schemes, and to determine how many of them have obtained employment. Centrally

sponsored and state-managed (CSSM) PMKVY 3.0 is executed by GSDM under the STT, RPL, and special projects categories across Gujarat.

4.1 CSSM Component of Gujarat

Of 3640 enrolled candidates in CSSM-STT, 2774 candidates were certified, out of which 2092 were female and 682 were male candidates. Of 6797 enrolled candidates in CSSM-RPL, 4749 candidates were certified, out of which 2916 were female and 1833 were male candidates (see Table 2).

Table 2: Gender-wise Certified and Non-certified Number of Candidates

	Male	Female	Total
STT			
Certified	682	2092	2774
Not Certified	275	591	866
Total	957	2683	3640
RPL			
Certified	1833	2916	4749
Not Certified	917	1131	2048
Total	2750	4047	6797

Table 3: Top 5 Job Roles (Certified)

Job Role - STT	Frequency	Job Role - RPL	Frequency
Self-employed Tailor	698 (25.16 %)	Self-employed Tailor	1476 (31.08 %)
General Duty Assistant	273 (9.84 %)	Beauty Therapist/Hairdresser/ Make-up Artist	848 (17.86 %)
Solar Panel Installation Technician	213 (7.68 %)	General Duty Assistant	579 (12.19%)
Field Technician Computing and Peripherals	195 (7.03 %)	Automotive Service Technician Level 4	291 (6.13 %)
Fashion Designer	150 (5.41 %)	Solar Panel Installation Technician	269 (5.66 %)

Notes: Top 5 job roles of certified candidates; Percentages are in parentheses.

Table 3 shows that the Self-employed Tailor was the most common job role, with 25.16% of respondents receiving training under the STT category from certified candidates in Gujarat (see, for details, Appendix Table A1). It also shows the top five job roles offered by training centres in Gujarat under the STT category. The Self-employed Tailor was the top job role with 31.08% of respondents receiving training, followed by Beauty Therapist under the RPL category from the certified candidates of Gujarat (see, for details, Appendix Table A2). Solar Panel Installation Technician was the most selected job role among male candidates, and Self-employed Tailor was the most selected job role among female candidates in the STT category from Gujarat state. The plumber was the most selected job role among male candidates, and the Self-employed Tailor was the most selected job role among female candidates in the RPL category (see Table 3).

4.2 Primary Data Analysis

A total of 779 sample respondents (465 for STT and 314 for RPL) were collected from the selected eight districts of Gujarat state. A quantitative analysis was done with primary data collected from the selected districts.

Table 4: Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Particulars	STT		RPL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Gender				
Male	135	29.0	119	37.9
Female	330	71.0	195	62.1
Category				
General	231	49.7	145	46.2
OBC	184	39.6	132	42.0
SC	41	8.8	31	9.9
ST	8	1.7	6	1.9
EWS	1	.2	1	.2
Marital Status				
Married	248	53.3	180	57.3
Unmarried	215	46.2	130	41.4
Widow	2	.4	4	1.3
Education				
Below Secondary	76	16.3	45	14.3
Secondary	162	34.8	124	39.5
Higher Secondary	147	31.6	78	24.8
Graduation	70	15.1	58	18.5
Post-graduation	10	2.2	9	2.9

Notes: OBC – Other backward class; SC – Scheduled caste; ST – Scheduled tribe; and EWS – Economically weaker section.

Of 465 STT respondents, 71% were female; the majority (90%) belonged to the General and OBC categories; the majority were in the 20-25 years age group; 54% were married; and had Higher Secondary or below Higher Secondary qualification. Of 314 RPL respondents, 62% were female; the majority (82%) belonged to the General and OBC categories; the majority were in the 20-40 years age group; 57% were married; and 54% of candidates had secondary or below secondary qualification (see Table 4).

4.2.1 Analysis of Training Effectiveness and Impact Assessment of STT Beneficiaries

Only 9.2% of total STT respondents possessed work experience between one and four years before joining the STT training programme (Figure 1). The majority of STT respondents had a six-month training program, with an average of 4 hours of classroom training, as well as practical training and study materials provided to them.

Among the total beneficiaries, the majority rated the quality of training, the efficiency of trainers, and the infrastructure at the training centre as excellent (Figure 2). The majority of RPL beneficiaries had technical know-how regarding their selected job roles before the training programme, and the majority of them were given one to two days of training (five to six hours per day), and 3 out of 5 received training materials as well. The majority of respondents rated the

training programme as excellent in terms of the quality of training, the trainers' efficiency, and the facilities provided by the training centre (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Number of Years of Work Experience Prior to Training

Figure 2: Quality of Training, Efficiency of Trainer, and Infrastructure Facilities in STT (%)

Note: Quality of training, efficiency of trainer, and infrastructure facilities in STT (%) are shown from poor-to-excellent scale, respectively.

Figure 3: Quality of Training, Efficiency of Trainer, and Infrastructure Facilities in RPL (%)

Note: Quality of training, efficiency of trainer, and infrastructure facilities in RPL (%) are shown from poor-to-excellent scale, respectively.

Table 5: Major Reasons for Joining the Training Programme

STT Training	Frequency	RPL Training	Frequency
Would help in getting employment	313 (67.3 %)	To Increase Income	208 (66.2 %)
Interest in the course	239 (51.4 %)	To get new career/employment opportunities	95 (30.3 %)
Would help increase income	269 (57.8 %)	As colleagues/friends had participated	79 (25.2 %)
To utilize their time due to unemployment	296 (63.7 %)	To increase their subject knowledge	163 (67.3 %)
Wanted to start own business/work	168 (36.1 %)	As employers made it mandatory	37 (51.9 %)
Suggested by friends/family	64 (13.8 %)	To get credibility for the experience	131 (41.7%)
Other reasons	6 (1.3 %)	To get a monetary incentive	113 (36 %)
		Other reasons	49 (15.6 %)

Note: Percentages are given in parentheses.

Most candidates join the STT training programme because it helps them get employment, utilise their time during unemployment, and increase their income. The main reasons for RPL beneficiaries joining such a training programme were to increase their income and their subject knowledge (see Table 5).

Figure 4: Expected Benefits from the STT Training (%)

The expected benefits of the training programme (multiple options were selected by the beneficiaries) for the majority of respondents were to increase their employability through certification and to create opportunities to increase their income (Figure 4). The majority of beneficiaries felt that, through the training programme, their soft and technical skills for their current jobs had improved (multiple options were selected by the beneficiaries) (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Perceived Benefits from RPL Training (%)

Table 6: Role of PMKVY Training in Current Employment

Role of PMKVY Training in Current Employment	Frequency	Percentage
Improving ability to work on the job	83	17.8
Improving technical skills required for the job	94	20.2
Improving soft skills required in the job	117	25.2
Increasing chances of getting employment	66	14.2

The majority of beneficiaries report that, through the training programme, their soft and technical skills required for their current jobs have improved (see Table 6).

Table 7: Average Monthly Income/Salary Increase before and after Training

Category	Before Training (in Rs.)	After Training (in Rs.)	Difference (in Rs.)
STT	8,625	10,133	1,508
RPL	7,800	7,855	855

Note: Average monthly income before and after training

Very few beneficiaries were employed after training in the STT and RPL categories. However, a visible rise in income was observed among self-employed and salaried beneficiaries of STT and RPL. In the STT category, the salary/income hike was Rs. 1,508 and Rs. 855 in RPL beneficiaries (see Table 7).

4.2.2 Hypothesis Testing

H01: There is a significant difference in quality of training, efficiency of trainer and infrastructure/facilities of training centres between male and female beneficiaries.

Table 8: Group Statistics

Particular	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Quality of training	Male	135	6.44	.843	.073
	Female	330	5.91	1.271	.070
Efficiency of trainer	Male	135	6.37	.862	.074
	Female	330	5.91	1.256	.069
Infrastructure/facilities provided by training centre	Male	135	6.47	.771	.066
	Female	330	6.10	.983	.054

Note: Mean values are shown for male ($n = 135$) and female ($n = 330$).

Table 9: Independent Sample t-test Table

Particular	Assumption	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Quality of training	Equal variances assumed	24.39	.000	4.442	463	.000
	Equal variances not assumed			5.239	369.05	.000
Efficiency of the trainer	Equal variances assumed	14.98	.000	3.906	463	.000
	Equal variances not assumed			4.549	358.11	.000
Infrastructure/facilities provided by the training centre	Equal variances assumed	6.760	.010	3.874	463	.000
	Equal variances not assumed			4.284	314.78	.000

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to assess differences in male and female beneficiaries' ratings of training quality. Given the significant p-value, the null hypotheses were rejected, and a significant difference was found in the quality of training, the efficiency of trainers, and the infrastructure/facilities available at training centres (see Tables 8 and 9).

4.3 Crosstabulation Results

The crosstabulation results for the STP sample reveal a stark economic stratification defined by gender-based income tiers and occupational specialization. Of 465 respondents, the 43 individuals active in the workforce prior to enrollment exhibited a binary earning structure: male participants ($n = 19$) were situated almost exclusively within the upper-income brackets, ranging from Rs. 10,000 to Rs. 25,000, while female participants ($n = 24$) were predominantly relegated to the lower economic strata of Rs. 4,000 or less. This disparity is fundamentally linked to occupational segregation; technical roles such as Solar Panel Installation Technicians ($n = 13$) commanded the highest sustained monthly incomes, whereas service and craft-oriented roles, including Sewing Machine Operators and Beauty Therapists, were confined to the lower end of the fiscal spectrum, consistently earning below Rs. 5,000.

A parallel analysis of the RPL program further validates these findings, demonstrating a significant association between specific trades and earning potential among the 93 self-employed respondents. Within this group, a substantial majority of men (41 out of 51) earned Rs. 8,000 or more, whereas more than half of the women (22 out of 42) earned Rs. 5,000 or less. While technical trades like Mechanics and Plumbers maintained stable concentrations in the Rs. 8,000-to-12,000 range, traditional occupations such as Tailoring ($n = 30$) displayed high income volatility, with earnings fluctuating from as low as Rs. 400 to Rs. 10,000. The data indicate that while a modal

income of Rs. 10,000 exists across diverse roles, service-oriented positions such as housemaids and parlour workers remain systematically trapped in the lowest income deciles.

The empirical evidence from these crosstabulations suggests that while technical specialisation is a primary gateway to higher monthly earnings, gender remains a dominant and persistent predictor of earning potential. The over-representation of women in low-paying manual and service sectors, contrasted with male dominance in high-yield technical tiers, underscores a structural gender-income gap that precedes professional training interventions.

4.4 Challenges/Constraints

- Based on the interview with officials of GSDM, major challenges reported by them in the implementation of the PMKVY CSSM component are as follows:
- Delays in the release of funds from the State Treasury to respective SSDMs/Departments.
- The absence of a Financial Disbursal IT module for CSSM leads to payment delays and tracking issues.
- Challenges related to PFMS and DBT systems.
- Pending assessments with Sector Skills Councils.
- Limited availability of Trainers meeting the required Eligibility Criteria.
- Scarce or insufficient Placement Partners due to less industrial linkage network.

Delayed payments to SSCs and Training Providers (TPs).

- Based on the discussion with the industry partners, the following constraints were observed:
- The training courses and curriculum offered by PMKVY were not fully synchronized with the real industry demands.
- Practical skills imparted during PMKVY training did not match industry requirements adequately.
- Reporting placement details of candidates under PMKVY was difficult and demanded significant effort.

4.5 Other Issues

- Throughout the implementation phases of PMKVY 1.0 and 2.0, it was observed that approximately 20% of enrolled candidates discontinued their training; however, in PMKVY 3.0, CSSM, 10% dropout was found. It was more in the RPL category compared to STT in CSSM.
- The reasons for candidate dropouts are in line with the evaluation study conducted by the Indian Institute of Public Administration (IIPA), New Delhi.
- These included medical issues, family obligations, social challenges, geographical distance between residence and training centres, aspirations for social advancement through marriage, livelihood commitments, lack of job opportunities, and perceived inadequacy in skill improvement from the course content or training program.
- Additionally, several female candidates cited reasons such as pregnancy, marriage, and the short duration of courses for their withdrawal from the program.

4.6 Mapping Job-roles with Sector Skill Councils

The MSDE has identified 37 skills across industries and DSCs to meet manpower requirements

across various sectors. The skills gap study was done with the various job roles offered in the STT and RPL categories of the CSSM component. Under the CSSM component, only 7 sector skills were covered in STT and RPL training across the 37 SSCs. Under the STT category, 16% of job roles were offered in the Electronics and IT Hardware sectors, followed by 12% in the Beauty & Wellness sector. Under the STT category, 41% of job roles were offered in the Textile sector, followed by 19% in the Retail sector (see Table 10).

Table 10: Sector Skills Mapping with Job Roles Offered

Sector	STT (%)	RPL (%)
Electronics and IT Hardware	15.7	3.8
IT and ITES	6.9	2.9
Auto and Auto Components	9.2	16.2
Retail	9.5	18.8
Textiles Sector	44	40.8
Beauty and Wellness	11.8	11.8
Construction	-	6
Capital Goods	2.2	-

4.7 Findings of STT

The study cohort of 465 participants showed a distinct female predominance and a demographic concentration in early adulthood, specifically the 20-25 age bracket. Socially, the sample was largely represented by the General and OBC categories, with a majority of respondents being married and possessing an educational background of Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC) or below. The socioeconomic profile indicated that most participants resided in medium-sized households of four to six members supported by a limited earning capacity, typically involving only one or two individuals. Furthermore, the economic status of these households was consistently below the lower-income threshold, with annual earnings primarily ranging from one lakh to two lakh rupees. The majority of respondents had no prior work experience. Self-employed tailors and Solar Panel Installation Technicians were the most selected job roles among female and male candidates from selected districts of Gujarat.

Average three to six months of training duration and three to six hours of daily training for different job roles. Both classroom study and practical training were used to impart training. The majority of respondents received study material from the training centres to get more insight into the training. It was found that very few candidates had paid the training fees. Beneficiaries were highly satisfied with the quality of training, the trainer's efficiency, and the infrastructure/facilities provided at the training centres.

Helping them get employment and utilise their time during unemployment were the major reasons for joining this training. Increased chances of employability due to certification and the opportunity to increase income were the perceived benefits of joining this training. The findings indicate a significant gap in institutional support, as the absence of placement assistance at training centres left the majority of candidates unemployed. Vocational outcomes were diverse but limited; while a negligible portion of the sample secured employment directly through their certification, a notable segment transitioned into self-employment or accepted roles unrelated to their specific training. Interestingly, the data suggest that non-placement was frequently driven by a lack of active job-seeking among more than half of the participants, whereas a smaller part faced systemic

unemployment despite actively seeking work.

Despite these placement challenges, the training program generated clear economic benefits, as evidenced by the improved monthly income of those who secured employment or became self-employed. Consequently, the training program maintained high institutional value, with participants overwhelmingly recommending the training to their social and familial networks. However, this training was not found to be significant in improving work ability, technical skills, soft skills, or increasing the chances of employment.

4.8 Findings of RPL

The survey sample of 314 respondents showed a demographic tilt toward female participants, with a substantial majority identifying as General or OBC. The age distribution primarily spanned the 20–40 years cohort, and a significant portion of the group was married. Educationally, over half of the candidates possessed a Secondary School Certificate (SSC) or lower qualification. The socioeconomic structure was characterized by medium-sized households of four to six members supported by a narrow earning base, typically relying on only one or two providers, with annual family incomes concentrated in the one to three lakh rupee range. While most respondents entered the program without prior professional work experience, there was a near-universal familiarity with the specific job roles associated with the training, indicating high levels of pre-existing vocational awareness.

The Self-employed tailors and Automotive service technicians (level 4) were the top-selected job roles among female and male candidates from selected districts of Gujarat. Average one to three weeks of training duration and three to six hours of daily training for different job roles. Both classroom study and practical training were used to impart training. The majority of respondents received study material from the training centres to get more insight into the training. Beneficiaries gave high ratings for the quality of training, the trainer's efficiency, and the infrastructure/facilities provided at the training centres.

Increasing income and subject knowledge were the main reasons for joining this training. Increasing self-confidence and developing an entrepreneurial attitude were the perceived benefits of joining this training. The majority of candidates received an orientation, training, and training materials during this training.

No candidates received placement at any training centres, as this training was used to obtain certification for their prior learning. Candidates gave high ratings for improvement in their job skills, confidence, and personality after this training program. This high level of perceived value is reflected in the nearly universal willingness of beneficiaries to endorse the program within their social and familial circles. Prior to enrollment, the cohort had diverse professional backgrounds, including individuals already established in similar roles, self-employed individuals, and others working in unrelated fields.

Post-training results indicate that a substantial majority of those who did not secure formal placement were not actively seeking new employment, as they remained committed to their existing self-employment ventures. In contrast, only a smaller segment of the population remained transitionally unemployed despite active job search, suggesting that the lack of formal placement was often a matter of participant intent rather than a lack of program efficacy. There was a noticeable increase in the monthly salary/income of candidates who received jobs or were self-employed after the training. The training proved beneficial for employment readiness and for enhancing the technical and soft skills required in current roles, but demonstrated limited effectiveness in securing

better employment opportunities.

5. Conclusions, Policy Recommendations and Limitations

The economy needs to fully harness the potential of its vast labour supply. Thus, based on the findings of this research, we came up with a set of policy suggestions as follows:

- *Placement and Industry Linkages:* Establish dedicated placement cells and industry-needs assessment mechanisms to connect STT/RPL candidates with employment opportunities. Launch pilot programs for emerging job roles and scale successful models statewide. Prioritize equal focus on training, certification, and verified placements (currently, 8% under PMKVY 3.0 vs 23% in 2.0).
- *Financial and Infrastructure Support:* Expedite grant releases to sustain motivation and innovation at the training centre. Upgrade ITI infrastructure and recruit qualified personnel for Industry 4.0 roles. Develop user-friendly online management systems across all States/UTs (currently functional in only 15 of 36).
- *Monitoring and Decentralized Implementation:* Strengthen GSDM monitoring to address data inaccuracies (duplicate IDs, missing contacts). Leverage District Skill Committees (DSCs) with ICT tools for real-time coordination. Conduct regular dialogues with industry training centres to align curricula with practical skill requirements.
- *Platform Optimization (ASEEM Portal):* Enhance ASEEM effectiveness by boosting employer registrations and active hiring (29 lakh registered vs 56,000 placed). Simplify placement reporting and integrate with job aggregators, apprenticeships, and special projects.
- *Dropout Mitigation Strategies:* Target 10-20% dropout individuals through accessible centres, flexible durations, and post-delivery training resumption for women via ASHA/Anganwadi networks. Address medical, family, distance, and marriage-related barriers with localized interventions.
- *Infrastructure and Centre Management (Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra):* Finalise the revised PMKK guidelines promptly and reallocate surrendered centres to new partners or to NSDC-owned facilities. Prioritise high-rental, underserved districts for optimal STT/RPL coverage (only 22/20 centres have been allocated by GSDM).
- *Employment Mela (Fair) Expansion:* Scale Kaushal (mobilization) and Rozgar Mela (placement fair) with intensified publicity via local representatives, cultural events, and digital channels. Focus on remote areas to boost STT/RPL beneficiary placements beyond current low coverage.

Finally, this study suffers from a number of limitations. They are listed below. Future studies should attempt to avoid these limitations.

- The sample is confined to eight districts of Gujarat and may not represent the entire state.
- Data collection was constrained by the closure of training centres after scheme completion, limiting on-site validation.
- Telephonic surveys may have introduced recall and non-response biases.
- Lack of pre- and post-training comparative data restricts the analysis of incremental impacts.
- The absence of ongoing training data limited the understanding of real-time learning environments.

Future studies could adopt longitudinal evaluation designs to compare pre- and post-training outcomes and include wider behavioural and sectoral variables to deepen policy insights.

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APPENDIX

Table A1: List of Job Roles under STT

Job Role	Certified	Not Certified	Total
Retail Team Leader / Retail Trainee Associate / Distributor Salesman	232	158	390
Assistant Electrician	0	77	77
Beauty Therapist / Hair Stylist / Hairdresser/ Make-up Artist / Pedicurist and Manicurist	259	40	299
Consignment Booking Assistant	117	61	178
CRM Domestic Voice	0	59	59
Documentation Assistant	17	13	30
Domestic Data Entry Operator	100	20	120
Draughtsman Mechanical	26	4	30
Export Assistant	60	0	60
Fashion Designer	150	0	150
Field Technician Computing and Peripherals	195	10	205
Field Technician Networking and Storage	85	3	88
Fitter: Levelling Alignment & Balancing	12	5	17
Fitter Fabrication	44	16	60
Front Office Associate	27	31	58
Gardener	25	0	25
General Duty Assistant	273	26	299
Goods & Services Tax (GST) Accounts Assistant	0	60	60
Home Health Aide	25	5	30
In-line Checker	28	1	29
Junior Software Developer	1	119	120
Medical Sales Representative	58	2	60
Self-employed Tailor / Sewing Machine Operator / Production Supervisor Sewing	698	78	776
Solar Panel Installation Technician	213	27	240
Solar PV Installer – Electrical	106	14	120
Warehouse Packer	23	37	60
Total	2774	866	3640

Table A2: List of Job Roles under RPL

Job Role	Certified	Not Certified	Total
Automotive Service Technician Level 4	291	109	400
Bamboo Utility Handicraft Assembler	46	3	49
Beauty Therapist / Hairdresser / Make-up Artist	848	297	1145
CCTV Installation Technician	127	123	250
Distributor Salesman	100	199	299
Export Assistant	99	1	100
Field Technician Computing and Peripherals	44	6	50
Field Technician Networking and Storage	86	14	100
Fitter Mechanical Assembly	46	54	100
General Duty Assistant	579	133	712
Mason General	86	17	103
Medical Sales Representative	0	49	49
Pickle Making Technician	92	6	98
Plumber (General)	413	136	549
Quality Control Chemist	8	78	86
Retail Sales Associate	101	205	306
Self Employed Tailor / Sewing Machine Operator	1476	325	1801
Solar Panel Installation Technician	269	131	400
Travel Consultant	38	162	200
Total	4749	2048	6797